

**PROCEEDINGS OF THE
3rd INTERNATIONAL
CSOUND CONFERENCE**

**Edited by
Gleb G. Rogozinsky**

ICSC 2015

Saint Petersburg, Russia
2 – 4 October 2015

The Bonch-Bruевич Saint Petersburg State
University of Telecommunications

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FOREWORD

Dear reader,

You have before you the proceedings of a unique conference. Csound is a computer music language that has been continually evolving since its inception in 1986. During that time it has united people of all ages from around the world and from a wide range of disciplines: audio technology, media programming, contemporary, academic and avant-garde music, digital signal processing, telecommunications and electronic dance music. The Csound community presents a unique forum of users where programming and compositional issues are discussed in equal measure and with equal energy.

A special aspect of this conference was that it took place in St. Petersburg, Russia: a city of great culture, world-renowned museums and beautiful white nights, and the city where Nikolay Rimsky-Korsakov and Dmitry Shostokovich wrote their most famous pieces. Without doubt, St. Petersburg merited hosting the 3rd International Csound Conference. Russia has great heritage in the world of electronic music, being the country from which the theremin and the ANS synthesizer originated, but in more recent times Russia has seen less innovation, so I am particularly proud to be able to contribute to remedying this by hosting this conference. I am sure that the conference will hold a unique place in the history of electronic music in Russia. It has been a pleasure to be able to establish a new Russian centre for Csound's world family.

The choice for the main location for the Conference was not entirely arbitrary. The Bonch-Bruевич St. Petersburg State University of Telecommunications is the region's biggest training facility in the field of telecommunications. The first computer program for sound synthesis, MUSIC (1957), was developed by Max Mathews at the world famous telecommunications research facility, Bell Labs in the USA, and as Csound is a direct descendant of this program it seems fitting that an association with telecommunications research continues. Telecommunications is the technology of technologies, changing the world every day, creating connections from human to human, human to machine, and more recently from machine to machine. I am pleased that Csound can take its place in this field, and also point to the future.

This document reflects the current state of Csound research and development. More than a hundred pages cover a wealth of topics: live coding, interactive installations, integration with other languages, commercial implementations and many more new developments.

Csound has a unique community, and I think these proceedings reflect this uniqueness in a most positive way. From the past to the future, from conference to conference, from version to version, the 'vessel' that is Csound leads the way to new horizons in computer music.

ICSC 2015 Chair

Gleb G. Rogozinsky

St. Petersburg, Spring 2016

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